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BENEFITS OF USING OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN THE PROCESS OF EVALUATING LEGAL TERMINOLOGY

Annotation

The paper examines using information technologies in the process of teaching and assessment of legal terminology for law students at Tashkent State University of Law. It also explains the benefits of using ICT in the process of teaching and assessment especially giving example of the program iSpring Quiz Maker and its possibilities. Indeed, legal English is of great importance since all practicing lawyers are required to work with international documents, cases and briefs. They become more privileged with legal English proficiency in both their studies and career. Therefore, the syllabus, all teaching materials, tests and assessment should meet learners' needs to enable them to develop all four skills in a foreign language.

Key words: Legal English, assessment, information technologies, law students, lawyers, legal terminology, language, communication.

ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ОЦЕНКИ ЮРИДИЧЕСКОЙ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИИ

Аннотация

В статье рассматривается использование информационных технологий в процессе обучения и оценки юридической терминологии студентов-юристов Ташкентского государственного юридического университета. Также объясняются преимущества использования ИКТ в процессе обучения и оценивания, особенно на примере программы iSpring Quiz Maker и ее возможностей. Действительно, юридический английский имеет большое значение, поскольку все практикующие юристы обязаны работать с международными документами, делами и договорами. У них больше привилегий, поскольку они владеют юридическим английским языком как в учебе, так и в карьере. Таким образом, учебная программа, все учебные материалы, тесты и оценки должны соответствовать потребностям учащихся, чтобы они могли развивать все четыре навыка владения иностранным языком.

Ключевые слова: Юридический английский, информационные технологии, оценка, учебная программа, студенты-юристы, юристы, юридическая терминология, язык, коммуникация.

YURIDIK TERMINLOGIYANI BAHOLASHDA AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING AFZALLIKLARI

Annotatsiya

Maqolada Toshkent davlat yuridik universitetining yuridik fakulteti talabalari uchun yuridik atamalarini o'qitish va baholash jarayonida axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish masalasi ko'rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, o'qitish va baholash jarayonida AKTdan foydalanishning afzalliklarini, xususan, iSpring Quiz Maker dasturi va uning imkoniyatlari misolida tahlil qilinadi. Darhaqiqat, yuridik ingliz tili katta ahamiyatga ega, chunki barcha amaliyotchi yuristlar xalqaro hujjatlar, ishlar va shartnomalar bilan ishlashlariga to'g'ri keladi. Yuridik ingliz tili savodxonligi esa ularga ham o'qishlarida ham mansabda ko'plab imtiyozga ega bo'lishlariga imkon beradi. Shu bois, o'quv dasturi, barcha o'quv materiallari, testlar va baholash talabalarining ehtiyojlariga mos kelishi kerak va shunda ular to'rtta chet tilini bilish ko'nikmasini takomillashtirishlari mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: Yuridik ingliz tili, axborot kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, baholash, o'quv dasturi, huquqshunos talabalar, yuristlar, yuridik terminologiya, til, kommunikatsiya.

Introduction. Over the past decades, international business activity has increased considerably. Thus, lawyers working in prestigious national structures began to cooperate with international clients, and draw contracts with companies located in various countries of the world, with different legal systems and traditions. For practical reasons, a large part of international legal activity is conducted in English, and most legal documents are written in English, or in English and additionally in another language. This means that lawyers around the world need to learn the basics of legal English. In addition, they need to learn to understand the language of legal documents, which is difficult for most native speakers due to complex syntax, specialized vocabulary and the use of archaic formulas. It is generally recognized that legal English, that is, "legalese", is difficult even for native English speakers. Both oral and written forms of legal language are not always

understood even by educated native speakers, and it is difficult for them to understand the language used in court proceedings. Before discussing teaching of legal English and its assessment, it is necessary to analyze the main characteristics of legal English. Because of the degree of complexity it presents, the focus of legal English teaching research is often on vocabulary, and didactic material designed to introduce students to this complex area often focuses on combination of terminology and content. Teaching English for preparing students who will be involved in legal activities requires special attention. From this point of view, it is impossible to teach legal English in isolation from a specific legal context. Since there are many legal terms, not only the process of teaching but also evaluation causes some difficulties for teachers. For this purpose, it is very important to use information technology in the learning process. As we know, there has been a huge

development in ICT (information and communication technology) in recent years and it is used in almost all areas of life, including education. The use of ICT in education has recently begun to attract potential and significant progress in language learning in Uzbekistan.

Literature review. The use of ICT in education is an integral part of learning, which can make the process of language learning easier for teachers and students. Several years have passed since the computer entered our lives, and we no longer imagine a modern lesson without the use of ICT. As Hartoyo (2008) noted in his book, computer is a tool and a capability that makes it easier for people to learn a language, although the effectiveness of learning depends entirely on the users. [1;56] Technology in this era has grown not only in quality but also in efficiency. The need for innovative technologies has led to a revolution in communication and the rapid development of the application of technology in teaching and learning. This technology has contributed to the improvement of language communication. Many types of applications that are used in the classroom have improved the learning process. Currently, computer is an effective assistant and an integral part of our lives, which allows us to improve the quality of training and the effectiveness of the process controlling. Therefore, using information technologies in educational process is very important. Using presentations allows teachers to enhance the learning of educational materials by students and conducting classes at a qualitatively new level, instead of using ordinary boards, showing slide films from a computer screen to a large wall screen or personal computer (laptop) for each student. Colourfully designed presentations can solve the problem of visual materials. A recent program that can help teachers energize and facilitate the assessment of legal terminology is iSpring Quiz Maker, which allows users to create smart quizzes using advanced features such as branching scripts, learning controls, and customizing feedback. There are 23 question types, including multiple choice, true/false, filling the blanks, drag-and-drop questions, and more, which can be widely used in the learning and learning process. Educators can completely design the design of short quizzes, as well as record and paste audio or video files, images, and even formulas. A flexible scoring system allows teachers to make a unique assessment of a student's knowledge. For example, author can set passing score by points or percentages, award special points for correct answers, and set their own rules for deducting points for incorrect answers or partial answers to the questions. In 2011, iSpring QuizMaker received the Brandon Hall Bronze Medal for "Best Promotion in Testing or Teaching Technology"[3].

Research methodology. The iSpring Free model also has Free QuizMaker, which provides all the core features of iSpring QuizMaker and generates SCORM-compliant courses. The very first step in creating quizzes in iSpring is choosing the questions you would like to create. The next step is how to add questions to your quiz. There are question types ranging from True/False to Blank. The amount of customizable options available for your tests is enormous. With iSpring's QuizMaker, you can actually make the right quiz for your students in little time. Once you have chosen the types of questions you want in your test, it is now a simple process of editing the text to suit your needs. After you complete the test, the only step is to start the presentation. iSpring QuizMaker is a versatile tool that allows for extensive customization and ease of use. The questionnaires and tests you create can be easily imported into your projects to create a presentation that not only informs but also tests your users' knowledge.

Analysis and results. In general, the benefits of ICT in the process of teaching a foreign language and its assessment can be summarized as follows:

- technology facilitates access to authentic language;
- technology provides access to wider sources of information and a variety of languages;
- technology enables people to communicate with the outside world;
- technology enables a learner-centered approach;
- technology develops learner autonomy. ICTs help people to get information and communicate with each other in a wider range.

In the context of language learning, ICT plays an important role as a "media", overcoming and facilitating the learning process, or direct communication between learners and the teacher, although they are not present in the same room or place at a certain time. Language learning program can be created so that students can study lessons with instructions, information, or additional explanations. ICT in language learning is used as a reference. A computer can store an unlimited amount of information or links that can be accessed anytime, anywhere. Fitzpatrick and Davis and Hartoyo outline seven ways in which ICTs can be used in language learning:

- a) Presentation some language learning materials, such as text materials, audio-videos, should be presented to learners. The presentation helps students to master the educational material well.
- b) Practice some types of exercises can be supported by ICT, including presentation stimuli in various combinations of text, audio and video formats. ICT also makes it possible to analyze student responses with appropriate feedback [1].
- c) Creation when using ICT in language teaching, a teacher can either purchase ready-made materials or create their own learning materials using various authoring tools.
- d) Computer assessment plays an increasingly important role in the teaching and learning of a foreign language. These tools were used to test and evaluate students' understanding after taking some of the courses.
- e) Publishing. There are ICT tools that help teachers and pupils or students to publish or link their work to a local network. The teacher and students can use ICT to publish their work in the following ways: - Word processors and Desk Top Publishing (DTP) software - Making audio recordings and editing tools to record interviews, discussions, teaching materials. - Using digital camera and camcorder to record presentations, drama, role-play. - Power point can be used as a medium for publishing presentations - Web pages using web development tools
- f) Communication. Technology can help students and teachers communicate with others. Some ICT tools that can be used as a medium are: 1) email, which allows language learners to communicate with "web friends" in other countries; 2) Tandem training; 3) computer alert; 4) web learning environment; 5) audio conferences; 6) Videoconferencing.
- g) Simulation. The computer can act as a stimulus that summarizes analysis, critical thinking, discussion and writing. However, there are both advantages and disadvantages of ICT and in the process of language learning reduces the intimacy of the relationship between the teacher and students, which can negatively affect the emotional feelings of students in the learning process.

Conclusion. ICT is presented as a "bridge" to overcome the distance and "survive" learning. In the case of distance, teachers can use ICT via videoconferencing so that they can teach or supervise the learning process of students. Therefore, the development of ICT is seen as the best way to teach and learn a particular language compared to existing

methods. The use of tests prepared by the ISpring Quiz Maker program to test students' knowledge increases their objectivity and allows you to determine the level of independent work, the nature of the student's thinking, which generally improves

the effectiveness of the educational process. The fulfillment by students of test tasks and their subsequent analysis by the teacher helps to correct the educational process in a timely manner, to find an individual approach to each student.

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